

Role of Knowledge Management in Effectiveness of Financial Decision Making: A practical study in branches of Al-Rasheed Bank of Kerbala Governorate – Iraq

Ghaith Saadi Mohammed Ali¹, Dr. Layla Mohsin Hasan², Alaa Hussein Fadhil³, Dr. Ahmed Abdullah Amanah⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Faculty of Administration and Economics, University of Kerbala, Iraq

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7259-7086>¹

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6380-0094>²

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5418-5464>³

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5092-391X>⁴

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Corresponding Author:

Dr. Ahmed Abdullah
Amanah

ABSTRACT

This study sheds light on role and importance of knowledge management in effectiveness of the process of making and taking financial and vital decisions at the level of Iraqi banking institutions. The main objective of the study is to focus attention of management of banks, study community, to importance of knowledge management with its dimensions in enhancing effectiveness of financial decision-making process in it. Al-Rasheed Bank, with its branch spread in Karbala Governorate, was selected as a community for current study. The questionnaire, which numbered (40), was distributed to various directors of departments, people's officials, and administrative and financial units in bank. Some statistical indicators (descriptive and analytical) available in statistical program (SPSS) were used. The most important finding of study is existence of a correlation relationship and a significant effect between study variables included in first and second main hypotheses in order to achieve effectiveness of financial decision-making in branches of Al-Rasheed Bank, Karbala, by adopting the dimensions of knowledge management.

KEYWORDS: knowledge management, financial decision-making, Al-Rasheed Bank - Iraq.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, intellectual and scientific developments have accelerated in various fields of knowledge management worldwide, and perhaps one preceded the other, and helped each other give it additional impetus. and to contribute to the achievement of other goals of the organization. There are many reasons for this acceleration, perhaps the most important of which lies in intense competition, globalization, rapid environmental change, and other developments on the international scene. These developments were directly reflected in the banking business, so banks in developed countries supported the developments in technology and helped support their research. helped in this endeavor. On the other hand, we see that there is a big gap between third world banks, including our Iraqi banks, and other banks, as some of our banks are trying hard to bridge that gap by adopting various strategic options.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is one of the most popular topics at the present time. The question here is what does knowledge management mean? What is the reason behind its importance in all organizations today? In this regard, (Al-Kubaisi) points out that the beginning of the eighties until the mid-nineties of the twentieth century represents the stage of interest and orientation towards knowledge management, and the actual beginning of knowledge management was in the mid-ninth decade of the twentieth century, and as it is called (Al-Kubaisi) the stage of maturity and recognition of knowledge management, specifically When the American company (HP) implemented the successful programs of the Knowledge Initiative, and in the applications of (Skandia) Insurance Company, the Canadian Imperial Bank, Beckmann Laboratories and the Du Chemicals Organization.

In order to shed light on the concept of knowledge management, knowledge management has been mentioned in various concepts by many researchers (Al-Kubaisi, 2002:58).

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Below is a table showing the opinions of some of them on the concept of knowledge management.

Table (2) Concepts of knowledge management according to opinions of some researchers

	Researchers	Year	Concepts of knowledge management
1	Laudon & Laudon	2000	A systematic and effective administrative process that leads to the storage of knowledge in the organization, and that information systems play their role in knowledge management by helping the organization to increase the flow of information and contain the knowledge base.
2	Hellriegel et al.,	2001	It is the art of adding value represented by the systemic effectiveness of know-how technology, the experiences used, and the issuance of judgments that have the need, whether inside or outside the organization, and that knowledge management is a means to increase satisfaction.
2	Daft	2001	It is a new way of thinking that revolves around organization and participation in the organization as well as interest (intelligence and creative resources), and is related to systemic efforts, how to provide intellectual capital and accelerate the provision of culture, continuous learning and sharing of knowledge, all of which will enter into building organizational activities.
4	Al-Kubaisi	2002	It is the term that expresses the behaviors and tools that the beneficiaries of the organization participate in formulating and performing to acquire the required knowledge and reflect it in business operations to reach the best applications with the intent of long-term competition and adaptation.

And by converging with the above researchers’ opinions about knowledge management and that it is a term, means, art, or a new way of thinking and as an administrative process and other names, the researcher sees [that knowledge management - is the process of organizing, developing and employing knowledge resources such as intelligence, experience, information, intuition as well as knowledge About the customer, competitors, the market and making it in the service of the organization and customers with its reflection on the business activity, in the sense of making knowledge resources in a continuous dynamic, taking with interest all changes and surrounding conditions in order to maintain the permanence of the organization and achieve lasting success over its competitors].

Importance of knowledge management lies in the organization’s focus on knowledge and how to manage it. Over the years, interest in knowledge management has increased because it constitutes the right direction towards innovation, and it no longer focuses on the assets and capital of the organization, but rather on the intellectual assets represented by knowledge and how to manage it, and it has become the first guide in Achieving an increase in profits for specialized services organizations such as accounts, lawyers, investment banks, advertising agents, management consulting, all of them focus on knowledge management directly, as they work to develop knowledge among their working staff to reflect it in the form of benefits for customers (Tampoe, 2000:48-45 & Mocmillan). The basic economic resources of workers and capital are no longer sufficient unless they are complemented by knowledge management.

Peter Draker used the term (knowledge work) in the sixties, and in recent years, specifically in the nineties of the twentieth century, work began with knowledge management - this asset that must be managed in the same way as (resources of the organization) are managed, so organizations resorted to emphasizing that it be Among the learning organizations and considering knowledge management is the critical work for the organizational organization (Daft, 2001: 257). And it confirms (Blomgvist, 2001:1-2 & Kylaheiko). The organizations focused on the issue of competition based on modern knowledge, which relies more on intellectual capital. There are many activities that help modernize knowledge management, including innovation and knowledge transfer. In this way, (Darosh, 2001:23) indicates that it is not possible to consider knowledge management The process of receiving information, storing it and organizing it for the purposes of use, but it is a method for generating new knowledge, through learning and sharing knowledge in the whole organization, and that information technology is not sufficient to solve the problems of exploiting knowledge, but it employs information technology (Information Technology) through training, rehabilitation and human interaction with knowledge elements to achieve goals desired. (Macmillan & Tampoe, 2000: 48) highlights the role of the importance of knowledge management. If it is within the organization, it is considered one of the necessary competencies required to encourage workers to share knowledge, and to facilitate the transfer and sharing of knowledge to all places that the organization desires, which is the first way to build a competitive advantage. Which is one of the biggest

challenges that businesses face. According to (O'Brien, 2000: 360), knowledge management has now become the main strategic use of information technology, and many organizations are building what is called (knowledge management systems), for the purpose of managing organizational learning, in the organization. From the aforementioned, knowledge management is of great importance, as it is one of the important means that helps the organization to reach the goal it aspires to, because knowledge management does not represent the goal itself. Although the organization possesses data and information, it does not have knowledge that enables it to answer all the questions that will be directed to it, and therefore the main goal of knowledge management is to generate knowledge among workers, and every important work using knowledge in the organization, and this includes all processes, procedures, experiences and forecasts in addition to It includes the Internet and knowledge bases, and all the important actions of collecting, storing and sharing knowledge.

Objectives of knowledge management Knowledge management aims to obtain explicit and tacit knowledge and facilitate the use of this knowledge to innovate and create added value for the organization, and this goal is based on a new vision of the knowledge-based organization (Goodale, 2001: 17). In addition to (developing creativity), which is the general objective of knowledge management, this management aims to improve the rate of transparency, the level of documentation, knowledge retention, improvement of knowledge sharing, and the flow of communications (Maier & Remus, 2001:2). The objectives of knowledge management come as explained by (Alavi & Leidner, 2001:113) as follows:

1. Making knowledge clear and showing its role in the organization, through maps, yellow papers guide (a special form for knowledge and experience) and text tools.
2. Develop a knowledge-intensive culture by encouraging the accumulation of behaviors such as sharing (rather than hoarding) knowledge and proactively seeking to provide knowledge.
3. Establishing a knowledge infrastructure represented by a technical system, and a network of contacts between people according to space, time, and tools, and encouraging interaction and cooperation.

(Probst, 1998:20) indicated that there are three types of objectives for knowledge management in the organization, namely:

1. Normative knowledge goals: focus on creating a knowledge-sensitive culture within the organization through which knowledge is shared and developed to build the basic conditions for knowledge management.

2. Strategic objectives: focus on securing the organization's future knowledge needs, through an accurate description of the various knowledge capabilities required in the future. These are long-term goals that are determined by the higher administrative organizational levels.
3. Operational objectives: It seeks to determine how to secure the functioning of knowledge management at the executive level, ie to enable knowledge management to translate its tasks and functions into practice according to a detailed procedural and time plan. They are short term goals.

And (Rassoli, 2005:15) the goal of knowledge management is not to manage all knowledge, but to manage the most important knowledge of the organization through:

1. Applying the acquired knowledge and capabilities of the incoming work force to achieve specific organizational goals.
2. Obtaining appropriate information and delivering it to appropriate person at the appropriate time.
3. Helping people to generate, share and represent knowledge in ways that are measurable.

Knowledge Manager Because of the urgent need at the present time to apply knowledge management in today's organizations, it did not depend on studying and generating knowledge bases only, but rather created a new job called ((chief knowledge manager)) and he is the senior executive director in the organization, who manages knowledge programs It develops design programs and systems to find new sources of knowledge or to achieve the optimal use of available knowledge, through organizational and management processes (Laudon & Laudon, 2000: 435) and (Turban & Potter, 2001: 340-343) indicates that the main knowledge manager function that It is formed, plays a role in structuring the knowledge lever using information technology, and this function was created in the (Coca-Cola) organization in 1990, and then other organizations, and that one of the most important responsibilities (C.K.O) is to form the infrastructure for knowledge management and build the knowledge culture base And accomplish everything related to that, and confirms (Dimancescu & dwenger, 1996: 189-180) that the knowledge manager must achieve the following goals:

1. Supporting development based on vertical global expertise.
2. Being able to achieve coherent work, through geographical survey and composite teams.
3. Sharing knowledge that exists within geographical boundaries.
4. Introducing the crane and its strength to support national and indigenous experiences.
5. Providing services to local customers.
6. Linking with the information in the outside world represented by (commercial databases, the Internet, general news, e-mail).

As the achievement of these events from the knowledge manager is what made the organizations achieve success over the past years, and all organizations working in the application of knowledge management should form the function of the knowledge manager, because this makes the working individuals as well as the customers look at the organization in a different way.

Knowledge management processes Knowledge management, according to the opinion of researchers in its field, is a process, as (Al-Kubaisi: 2002, 67) indicated that knowledge derived from information and from both external and internal sources does not mean anything without those processes that enhance it and enable it to obtain it, participate in it, store it and preserve it for the purpose of Refer to it when needed, and that knowledge management processes are one of the sequential processes that complement each other, each one depends on the previous process and enhances the next process, and (Alter, 1999: 168) indicates that there are communication systems that contribute to facilitating these processes and depend on the available technology and email. (Piasecki & Fletcher, 1999: 167-169) believes that knowledge management processes are internally interrelated and include four activities:

1. **Defining knowledge:** It is an activity represented by testing data through the knowledge warehouses available to the organization. This process is considered one of the basic skills in the organization and can be achieved with the help of computer programs.
2. **Acquisition of knowledge:** It means the interdependence between information, such as the efforts made by the organization in preparing the documents necessary for the plan.
3. **Sharing knowledge:** It is the sharing of information such as lists of data necessary to provide raw materials or an emergency distribution plan, electronic messages or the internal Internet used in the organization.

4. **Storage of knowledge:** It is an activity aimed at documenting and preserving knowledge using the storage method in the complex environmental medium that surrounds it and providing facilities for the organization to provide the learning organizations that build and generate knowledge with the accumulated experience and knowledge as well as building knowledge management systems for the purpose of managing Organizational learning and (know-how) work, generating knowledge among workers, organizing and providing important work using knowledge in the organization, and the knowledge bases in the organization are responsible for collecting, storing and sharing knowledge (O'Brien, 2000: 360-361). (Bellinger, 2000: 1-2) comes with another opinion about knowledge management processes, which is a way to take advantage of directing and processing raw data and converting it into useful information, and in return that information can become knowledge that leads to wisdom. (Mcshane & Glinow, 2000: 20-21) shows that there are three basic knowledge management processes represented in:

1. Acquisition of knowledge by obtaining accurate information, and this is done either from learning individuals and observing the environment, vaccination and experience.
2. Sharing knowledge through the process of rapid and smooth communication of important information, as well as teams that include new members, which play an important role in sharing knowledge.
3. The benefits of knowledge management are evident in the workers' understanding and awareness of the information previously obtained, and then adapting to it. The following figure shows the processes of knowledge management as indicated by (Mchane & Glinow)

Figure (2) Knowledge Management Processes

1.2 Financial Decision Making

Decision-making is the basis and heart of management, and in many cases managers see that the decision-making

process is their primary work because they must constantly choose what should be done and who will do this work and when, where and how, and therefore the decision-making

process is by its nature a continuous and pervasive process. In the basic functions of management, in the financial function, we find that the financial manager is responsible for making financial decisions, and this is what we are trying to address in this study.

It expresses the nature of the command and direction between the levels of the administrative hierarchy, but in terms of content, it is considered to take a position in the face of a specific issue of a financial nature, i.e. related to the financial aspect of the institution. (Dabbas, 1983: 219) Financial decisions are characterized by characteristics, including:

- a. Financial decisions are often binding on the institution, and therefore great care must be taken when making these decisions.
- b. Financial decisions are crucial for the institution, as the success or failure of the institution depends on those decisions.
- c. The results of financial decisions do not appear quickly, but rather take a long time, which leads to the difficulty of correcting the error if those decisions are wrong (Ramadan, 1996: 12).

Steps in financial decision-making process: Decision-making is the process of choosing between distinct alternatives in order to achieve certain goals, and every process in which you make a financial decision must go through basic steps in order to reach the desired goals, and these steps are as follows:

1. **Defining the problem:** The decision-maker must clearly define the problem in front of him. His understanding of the problem helps to gather appropriate information and propose possible alternatives quickly and effectively, as he wins time and effort.
2. **Collecting data and information:** After defining the problem and knowing it well, the decision-maker collects all his money related to the problem before him in terms of data and information, whether it is quantitative or descriptive information. He can also rely on previous data, i.e. The institution indicates that it has occurred, and what is important here is that the data and information are appropriate to the nature of the required decision, and to take it so that it can gain the time as well as the costs necessary to solve the problem (Al-Budaiwi, 1997: 51).
3. **Proposing alternatives and choosing the appropriate alternative:** After collecting all the information related to the nature of the problem, the decision-maker will present the possible alternatives to solve the problem at hand, then he will define the criteria for selection and comparison between the different alternatives, i.e. setting criteria for evaluating the alternatives so that he can reach the alternative that achieves better than others. The objectives for which the decision will be made and this process is not easy, but there are some criteria that can be

used to help choose the best solution, including: (Tawfiq, 2000: 116).

- a. Risk: There is no work that is completely free of risk, and from it is necessary to compare the notification of each alternative solution with the expected gains from it.
- b. Saving effort: The best solution is the one that maximizes results and reduces effort, and therefore it is necessary to compare the expected results with the effort required to achieve them.
- c. Available resources and their limitations: No problem can be solved by means of an alternative unless the necessary resources are available for that, and among the most important of these necessary resources are human resources, that is, the individuals who implement the decision and who must have the skill, knowledge and authority that enables them to determine what they can do and what they can not.
- d. Decision-making: It is considered the last stage of decision-making, meaning that situations cannot be resolved without the decision, and the financial field, like other administrative fields, requires the authority to make decisions, meaning that the individual possesses the qualities and skills that enable him to make the greatest year of sound decisions (Hanafi, 2007: 34).

Types of financial decisions They are of two types, the long-term investment decision, and the long-term financing decision. My agencies:

1. **Long-term investment decision:** investment is defined as a link that aims to achieve expected gains over a long-term period in the future (Al-Hawari, 1984:30). etc. (Al-Hawari, p. 13) The investment decision is considered the most important, difficult and most dangerous decision taken by the financial management and the institution, because it depends entirely on forecasts, and also it must be taken into account that the new investment is in line with the activities, objectives and policies of the institution, as any error in estimating the importance of investment has serious consequences. The risk increases whenever the sums required to be invested are large, and whenever the economic conditions in the country are in rapid change, and the investment decision is not just an evaluation of alternatives only, but it is primarily pure and creating investment opportunities. New opportunities, in addition to the importance of studying about investment opportunities, studying about appropriate and accurate information is necessary to make a sound decision.
2. **Long-term financing decision:** Long-term financing represents the funds available to the institution to finance available investment opportunities, and it represents an

obligation on the institution as an independent legal personality, as this obligation represents another burden on the financial manager, as it forces him to have a full and accurate knowledge of the financial markets in terms of financing methods. The various methods available to it, the cost of each method, and the determination of the optimal financing structure for the institution that maximizes profit and the market value of the share. If it is decided to invest, the next decision is to choose the source of long-term financing, and this decision depends on choosing a sound financing structure that achieves a minimum level of risk or a higher level of profitability, according to the objective of the enterprise.

3. Medium-term financial decisions : This type of decision is represented in medium-term financing decisions, and the latter is used to finance a permanent need for the project, such as to cover fixed assets or to finance projects under implementation that take a number of years.

4. Short term financial decisions: Short-term financial decisions are considered practical decisions. The institution's activity includes several cycles that allow achieving the general goals, which are the exploitation cycle, the investment cycle, and the financing cycle. The exploitation cycle works on purchasing raw materials, storing them, coordinating them, and transforming them with the intervention of workers and technicians, such as tires and machines, and then restocking Products and selling them to customers. As for the financing cycle in the short term, it allows bringing in financial resources from private individuals and banks, then repaying them according to the previously specified conditions from the value of loans and interest payments to banks and vouchers to shareholders or partners.

For all of this, decisions must be made that allow reaching the set goals. Every decision taken in these operations is considered as a short-term financial decision. Therefore, the manager must predict and estimate the short term in a rather easy way, as short, three or four, or even monthly or even weekly. , approved and based on the accounting aspect through budgets that are consistent with medium-term plans, and to achieve this consistency, the preparation of budgets must be very accurate.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Problem: The administration takes modern administrative methods that have proven effective in achieving the distinguished decision through modern philosophy in scientific management, because this represents the organization obtaining knowledge characteristics that achieve the organization's direct interaction with the results to be achieved, and accordingly, interest in knowledge management is a logical result All modern departments turn

to him. Despite the importance that knowledge management occupies in financial decision-making, the management of Iraqi banks still follows randomness in its formulation; The problem can be formulated in a general question (Does knowledge management influence financial decision-making) and on this basis, the following questions can contribute to clarifying the problem:

- a. What is knowledge management? And can it be integrated with the practices and performance achieved to reach financial decision-making in the bank in the study community?
- b. What is the level of adoption of knowledge management in the study population?
- c. What is the level of relationship between knowledge management and financial decision-making in the bank, the study population?
- d. Do the managers of the bank in question have a clear perception of the dimensions of the role of knowledge management and its role in making financial decisions?

2.2 Study Importance: The importance of the study lies in its subject matter as it deals with the study of the role of knowledge management in financial decision-making by framing the literature related to the subject of knowledge management in financial decision-making and showing the scientific and practical importance for the study sample banks and the services provided by financial managers to improve the reality of banks by adopting knowledge management for decision-making Financial, and more specifically, the importance is determined by the following:

- a. Presenting the scientific foundations upon which the banks under study can rely in determining the relationship between knowledge management and financial decision-making in an Iraqi service environment represented by a sample of the banking sector.
- b. The rapid changes that the Iraqi banking environment will witness in light of the new transformations, as well as the emergence of a high level of competition, which is not limited to competition between governmental and private banks, but will include them in the circle of Arab and international competition, and when the Iraqi banking market opens up in the future in light of the change. What is new that requires these banks to pay more attention to knowledge management in order to achieve effectiveness in making financial decisions and to preserve their current sources?
- c. Providing information that helps all administrative officials in the researched bank and others to develop the level of financial decision-making.
- d. The subject of the study is important because it is one of the necessary subjects in the Iraqi financial service sector.

2.3 Study Objectives: By knowing the problem of study and its importance, study seeks to achieve following objectives:

- a. Measuring the sample's awareness of the variables of the study, knowledge management, and financial decision-making with their dimensions in the bank, the study community.
- b. Testing the correlation between knowledge management and the effectiveness of financial decision-making in the bank, the study population.
- c. Testing the impact of knowledge management on the effectiveness of financial decision-making in the bank, the study population, through regression models.
- d. Knowing the extent to which bank under study has contributed to the development of knowledge

management methods, which makes it capable of making an effective financial decision.

- e. Developing the future role of knowledge management in achieving the effectiveness of financial decision-making in the bank under study.

2.4 Hypothetical Study Model: In the light of the study problem and its questions and in order to achieve its objectives, a hypothetical scheme was developed to show the relationships between the variables of the study, knowledge management as an independent variable and financial decision-making as a dependent variable, as in Figure (1) below:

Figure (1) / Hypothetical Study Model

2.5 Study Hypotheses: In order to accept the hypothetical study plan or not, the following main hypotheses were formulated:

H1: There is a significant correlation between knowledge management and financial decision-making at the level of significance 0.05 in the Rasheed Bank, the study population.

H2: There is a significant influence relationship of knowledge management in financial decision-making at the level of significance 0.05 in the Rasheed Bank, the study population.

2.6 Study Spatial Limits: The governmental and private banking sector of the governmental Al-Rashid Bank in the holy city of Karbala, with its many branches, was chosen as a field of study for the following reasons:

- a. The great importance of the banking sector and its economic position in supplying the development movement with its needs of funds.
- b. Despite the importance of this, the studies conducted on it are still limited compared to the research and studies that focused on the industrial sector, which made it a fertile field for study.

2.7 Sources and methods of collecting data and information

In order to obtain the necessary information and data, which help in implementing the objectives of the study and reaching the results, the researcher relied on the following sources and methods:

- a. **Theoretical side:** The researcher relied in his coverage of the theoretical side of this study on the descriptive method, relying on published and unpublished references and sources as well as the global information network

(the Internet), in both Arabic and foreign languages related to the subject of the study, as well as the use of some documents and annual reports of banks Researched according to the needs of the study.

- b. **The practical side:** As for the practical side, the researcher relied on the use of the following means in collecting the information required for the study: personal interviews, as interviews were conducted with the bank manager, department managers, and officials of the administrative and financial units and divisions of the bank in question, with the aim of clarifying the paragraphs of the questionnaire in case of need This is to ensure the correct answer, in addition to asking indirect questions that serve the study and the employees of the bank in question.

- The use of some official documents: which are the annual reports of the bank in question.
- Questionnaire form: It is a major tool in data collection, if its formulation takes into account its ability to diagnose and measure study variables.
- Study Methodology Two main methods were used in collecting data related to subject of study:

- i. **The descriptive method:** through which the secondary data for the study was collected by using a number of scientific sources, research, studies and reports published in foreign and Arab scientific journals and periodicals, as well as the proceedings of scientific conferences, for the purpose of clarifying the basic concepts on the subject of the study, as well as enriching the discussion process hypotheses.

- ii. **The analytical survey method:** The primary data was collected through a field survey on a sample of the study population that included (50) questionnaires, and only (40) valid questionnaires were retrieved from the bank manager and officials of the departments and divisions of the study sample by distributing a questionnaire to find out their opinions on various aspects the study. The five-point Likert scale will be used.
- iii. **Measuring the validity and reliability of the study items:** In order to verify the validity and

reliability of the items of the study scale, the Cronbach alpha coefficient (Malhotra & Bries, 2000: 307) was adopted to determine the accuracy of the answers of the study sample. The values of the Cronbach alpha coefficient are statistically acceptable when they are equal to or greater than (70%), specifically in administrative and behavioral research. Table (1) shows the results and testing the validity and reliability of the study scale, as it shows that the Cronbach alpha coefficient reached 0.919 for the study scale as a whole.

Table (1) Reliability Statistics

	N. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	
Knowledge Management	9	.861	.919
Financial Decision-Making	16	.897	

3. RESULT

3.1 Description study sample: After the individuals to whom the questionnaire was addressed were identified, as a systematic, intentional sample was chosen from the banks, the study sample represented by the directors, heads of departments and officials of the branches of the Rasheed Bank, relying on the opinions of experts in the banking

business according to the influence criterion for each of them in drawing The strategy of the bank in which they work, in addition to their great experience in the field of banking work, as the researcher sought to define a scientifically accurate description of each individual through some criteria that were included with the questionnaire.

Table (3) Description study sample

Information	Category	Number	Percentage
Sex	Male	16	%40
	Female	24	%60
	Total	40	%100
Age	20 years or less	0	%0
	21-30	2	%5
	31- 40	18	%45
	41 - 50	4	%10
	51- 60	12	%30
	61 and over	4	%10
	Total	40	%100
Qualification	Secondary, less	2	%5
	Diploma	6	%15
	Bachelor	28	%70
	Higher Diploma	0	%0
	Master's	4	%10
	Ph.D	0	%0
	Total	40	%100
Year of job	1- 5	2	%5
	6 - 10	4	%10
	11 - 15	6	%15
	16 - 20	6	%15
	21 - 25	6	%15
	26 - 30	10	%25
	31 - or more	6	%15
	Total	40	%100

It is clear from Table (3) that most of the study sample are females, as their percentage reached 60% compared to 40% males, which is a good percentage, especially if we take into account the nature of the work of the banking reality in which the female component is present in such an activity. The age group, where the category (31-40) constitutes the highest percentage, which is 45%, then comes after it (51-60), followed by the two categories (41-50 and 61 and over) and then the rest of the other groups, which reflects the degree of maturity of the sample individuals that is consistent with the characteristics of individuals. The sample (manager) and the impact of this percentage on the ability to answer the paragraphs of the questionnaire towards what they enjoy of long life experience and spending it in the banking work, but in terms of (educational qualification) most of the study sample are those who hold a bachelor's degree, as their percentage represents 70 %, as for the diploma, it was 15%, while those who hold a master's degree were 10%, and this is consistent with the nature of the leadership tasks of the study sample and gives a good indication of the sample's answers for their ability to understand the questions and absorb their variables, while the length of service in the banking business,

which represents the indicator of the acquired service for individuals. In the sample, we find that most of the respondents have more service in the banking business. From 25 years, as its percentage of the study sample amounted to 25%, and this represents a positive point about the sincerity of the sample's answers about the questionnaire paragraphs, because this experience gives them banking capabilities and skills that are reflected in the ease of understanding the variables to be inquired about.

3.2 Description and Diagnosis of variables study

a. Knowledge management: Table (4) indicates frequency distributions, arithmetic mean, standard deviations, coefficients of variation, and (t) values calculated for the dimensions of knowledge management. (0.707), and that the coefficient of total difference is (0.166), and the calculated (t) value was (9.814), which is greater than its tabular value (1.684) with a degree of freedom of 40. As well as for the sub-dimensions, all of them were of acceptable percentages indicating the sample's awareness of the knowledge management variable and its sub-dimensions (explicit knowledge, tacit knowledge

Table (4) Description and Diagnosis of knowledge management

Paragraphs	arithmetic mean	deviation	difference	t-value
1	4.350	0.736	0.169	10.052
2	4.350	0.580	0.133	12.758
3	4.150	0.864	0.208	7.292
4	4.300	0.648	0.151	10.980
5	4.600	0.496	0.108	17.663
Explicit knowledge	4.350	0.685	0.158	10.787
6	4.250	0.707	0.166	9.682
7	4.600	0.591	0.128	14.840
8	4.500	0.751	0.167	10.938
9	4.550	0.749	0.165	11.329
Tacit knowledge	4.475	0.709	0.158	11.396
Knowledge Management	4.267	0.707	0.166	9.814

b. Financial Decision-Making: Table (5) indicates the frequency distributions, arithmetic mean, standard deviations, coefficients of variation, and (t) values calculated for the dimensions of financial decision-making, as the total weighted arithmetic mean was (4.177), which is greater than the hypothetical arithmetic mean of (3), and the total standard deviation is (0.804),

and that the coefficient of total variation is (0.193), and the calculated (t) value was (8.015), which is greater than its tabular value (1.684) with a degree of freedom of 40. As well as for the sub-dimensions, all of them were of acceptable percentages indicating the sample's awareness of the financial decision-making variable and its sub-dimensions (cost, quality, excellence).

Table (5) Description and Diagnosis of Financial Decision-Making

Paragraphs	arithmetic mean	deviation	difference	t-value
1	3.800	0.883	0.232	4.963
2	4.150	0.975	0.235	6.458
3	4.350	0.736	0.169	10.052

4	4.200	0.939	0.224	6.998
5	4.550	0.749	0.165	11.329
Cost	4.210	0.889	0.211	7.457
6	4.050	0.876	0.216	6.568
7	4.000	1.013	0.253	5.408
8	4.300	0.648	0.151	10.980
9	4.200	0.608	0.145	10.816
10	4.250	0.707	0.166	9.682
Quality	4.160	0.770	0.189	8.085
11	4.200	0.608	0.145	10.816
12	4.250	0.630	0.148	10.860
13	4.200	0.608	0.145	10.816
14	3.950	0.749	0.190	6.943
15	4.300	0.648	0.151	10.980
16	4.450	0.597	0.134	13.303
Excellence	4.225	0.640	0.129	10.619
Financial Decision-Making	4.177	0.804	0.193	8.015

3.3 Analyze and Test Correlation between variables of study

This paragraph focuses on measuring the correlation between the variables of the study included in the first main hypothesis, and the researcher used for this purpose the simple linear correlation coefficient (person), after that the significance of the correlation coefficients was tested using the (t) test. In order to give an accurate decision regarding the

validity of the first main hypothesis or not, which states (there is a significant correlation between the dimensions of knowledge management and financial decision-making) and in order to accept the above main hypothesis or not, the value of the simple correlation coefficient presented in Table (6) was tested. , using the (t) test, to find out the significant significance of the relationship between knowledge management (X) and financial decision making (Y).

Table (6) Correlation between Knowledge Management (X) and Financial Decision-Making (Y)

	KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT	VALUE (T)	RELATIONSHIP TYPE	
	CORRELATION COEFFICIENT	CALCULATED	TABULAR (5)%	THERE IS A SIGNIFICANT CORRELATION AT THE 5% LEVEL.
FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING	0.863	7.426	1.684	

It is clear from the results presented in Table (6), that there is a significant correlation at the level (5%) between the knowledge management variable (X) and financial decision-making (Y), as the value of the simple correlation coefficient between them was (0.863), and the value of (t) calculated (7.426), which is greater than the tabular (t) value of (1.684) at the level of significance (5%). It is clear from the above that the first main hypothesis is accepted.

3.4 Measuring Effect between variables of study

This paragraph aims to test the second main hypothesis, based on simple regression analysis, as well as using the coefficient of determination (R²) to explain the effect of independent variables on changes in the dependent variable,

in addition to the standard coefficient of regression BETA, which measures the response of the dependent variable when the independent variable changes with a single standard. The linear equation for simple linear regression, which was adopted within the SPSS28 program, is $Y = a + bX + e$. In order to give an accurate decision regarding the validity of the second main hypothesis or not, which is (there is a significant effect relationship between knowledge management and financial decision-making), morality was tested A simple linear regression model, using the (F) test, to determine the significance of the model for the purpose of determining the effect of knowledge management (X) on financial decision making (Y).

Table (7) Effect of Knowledge Management (X) on Financial Decision-Making (Y)

	CONSTANT	KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT	F		R ²	BETA
	A	B	CALCULATED	TABULAR (5) %		
FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING	1.762	0.583	111.228	2.16	0.745	0.863

Table (7) shows the parameters of the regression model used in the measurement according to the simple model, and therefore the interpretation of the relationship will be as follows:

- a. The value of the interpretation coefficient (R²) amounted to (0.745), meaning that the percentage of what is explained by the knowledge management variable (X) of the changes that occur in financial decision-making is (74.5%), while the remaining percentage, amounting to (25.5%), is due to the contribution of other variables outside the study.
- b. The value of the standard regression coefficient (Beta) of (0.863) means that any increase in the knowledge management variable (X) by one standard unit deviation will lead to an improvement in financial decision-making by.(%86.3)
- c. The calculated (F) value measures the significance of the simple regression model as it amounted to (111.228), which is greater than its tabular value of (2.16) by a large difference at the level of significance of 5%, which means that there is a significant influence relationship of knowledge management in enhancing the effectiveness of financial decision-making and thus Acceptance of the second main hypothesis, which states (there is a significant effect relationship of knowledge management in the effectiveness of financial decision-making) in the study population bank.

4. CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusions

4.1.1 Conclusions in Theoretical Side

- i. The literature showed remarkable agreement on the need to show the strategic role of knowledge management in relation to the effectiveness of financial decision-making as one of the contemporary issues in management thought in building and developing bank management relations with the financial market environment.
- ii. Knowledge management constitutes an effective entrance through which organizations can free their departments from surrendering to negative sources of information so that the bank's management can excel in making an effective financial decision.
- iii. Knowledge management has implications that do not stop at the limits of financial decision-making in supporting the bank's ability to face challenges

by updating and expanding its knowledge base to reach the satisfaction of senior management.

- iv. The analytical review of studies related to knowledge management showed a growing need for more practical and cognitive effort in studying and defining its applied and cognitive dimensions.

B. Conclusions in Practical Side

- i. The study sample banks pay varying attention to explicit knowledge in finding solutions to their problems, and these banks are proactive in informing the administration of the information that they wish to obtain in advance, as they inform the administration regarding their financial positions and profits.
- ii. There are different interests of the banks in the study sample with explicit knowledge in the field of knowledge of their financial positions and their endeavor to build and develop strategic relationships with them. There are surveys of their prospective vision to determine the future needs of banks, and there are perceptions and sufficient information about the degree of response of the financial market to those banks.
- iii. The interests of the study sample banks varied in the dimensions of financial decision-making
- iv. The results showed that the excellence dimension has achieved the first place in terms of its construction and development, depending on the dimensions of knowledge management.
- v. The results showed that the cost dimension achieved the second rank in terms of its construction and development, depending on the dimensions of knowledge management.
- vi. The results showed that the dimension of quality achieved the third rank in terms of its construction and development, depending on the dimensions of knowledge management.
- vii. The results show that the study sample banks are still competing to achieve economies of scale (cost savings) at a time when those banks pay significant attention to improving their knowledge capabilities in the field of knowledge management.
- viii. The results show that the study sample banks seek to achieve differentiation through the quality of banking services, and that their management is

concerned with the operations aimed at developing banking decisions.

- ix. It is inferred from the results of the study that the banks in the study sample seek to provide a wide variety of financial decisions to meet their needs from the ever-changing financial markets, and that they respond quickly to financial requests that differ in quantity and quality.

4.2 Recommendations

- i. Adopting the principle of transparency and financial dialogue in the practical performance of banks so that the administration can make the financial decision and know the level of performance of the bank and the points of shortcomings and strengths to enable the administration to submit proposals to benefit from them in development.
- ii. The need for the higher managements of the banks, the study sample, to depend on knowledge management in financial decision-making as a modern management philosophy that aims to educate banking leaders of the need to abandon traditional methods and systems of management in order to be able to reach excellence in financial decision-making.
- iii. Activating the financial decision-making process in the banks, the study sample, by documenting information related to financial decision-making in order to meet the bank's needs efficiently and to preserve it from moving to other banks.
- iv. Establishing a subsidiary department in each bank under the name (Knowledge Management) that appears in the organizational structure and defines its tasks by obtaining direct knowledge from the financial markets, storing, distributing, participating in and producing it. It can be linked to the information systems unit of the bank in order to work in an integrated manner and facilitate the task of making the necessary financial decisions.
- v. The need for the higher managements of banks to study the banking market in depth, study the financial decision-making process, determine its needs, and reduce the gap between what the management desires and what is actually provided.
- vi. Changing the performance evaluation mechanism of the management in the bank so that the financial decision-making process becomes distinct.
- vii. Building an institutional culture, one of the symbols of which is the philosophy of knowledge management, so that management believes in it and embodies it in their behavior and work so that the distinguished financial decision becomes frequent in the bank.
- viii. Establishing a unit to carry out financial market research and manage relations with decision-makers in order

to identify the needs of the bank, and this is done in light of the above point.

- ix. Encouraging the transfer of knowledge between the management of the bank and the financial decision makers of the bank.
- x. Encouraging advanced expertise in banks to present theoretical and practical lectures and discussions.
- xi. The need for the study sample banks to pay great attention to building and updating banking information systems that contribute to expanding the information base when making financial decisions to meet current and expected conditions, as well as to develop electronic networks within the framework of strengthening financial market relations with banks.

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